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РОЗВИТОК РОЗУМНОГО ЗРОСТАННЯ В УКРАЇНІ

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Предметом дослідження є розумне зростання.

Метою є дослідження теоретичних та практичних аспектів розвитку розумного зростання в Україні.

Методи, що були використані в процесі дослідження: метод порівняльного аналізу, узагальнення, статистичний та інші методи дослідження.

Результати роботи. Проаналізовано розумне зростання в Україні. Приділено увагу пріоритетам та цілям, які повинні бути ключовими в «Європі 2020», а їх досягнення матиме вирішальне значення для нашого успіху в 2020 році.

Галузь застосування результатів: Міністерство освіти і науки України, Міністерство фінансів України, Верховна Рада України.

Висновки. В Україні важливим напрямком діяльності держави і регіонів має стати розумне зростання, яке залежить від потенціалу вищої освіти, науки, вітчизняних фахівців, ролі університетів в інноваційному розвитку, технологічному та індустріальному розвитку регіональних та національної економіки.

Ключові слова: розумне зростання, інновації, глобалізація, синергетичний ефект, Стратегія сталого розвитку «Україна – 2020», європейська стратегія «Європа 2020», рамкова програма «Горизонт 2020».

РАЗВИТИЕ РАЗУМНОГО РОСТА В УКРАИНЕ

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Предметом исследования является разумный рост.

Целью является исследование теоретических и практических аспектов развития разумного роста в Украине.

Методы, использованные в процессе исследования: метод сравнительного анализа, обобщения, статистический и другие методы исследования.

Результаты работы. Проанализировано разумный рост в Украине. Уделено внимание приоритетам и целям, которые должны быть ключевыми в «Европе 2020», а их достижение будет иметь решающее значение для нашего успеха в 2020 году.

Область применения результатов: Министерство образования и науки Украины, Министерство финансов Украины, Верховная Рада Украины.

Выводы. В Украине важным направлением деятельности государства и регионов должен стать разумный рост, который зависит от потенциала высшего образования, науки, отечественных специалистов, роли университетов в инновационном развитии, технологическом и индустриальном развитии региональных и национальной экономики.

Ключевые слова: разумный рост, инновации, глобализация, синергетический эффект, Стратегия устойчивого развития «Украина – 2020», европейская стратегия «Европа 2020», рамочная программа «Горизонт 2020».

THE DEVELOPMENT OF REASONABLE GROWTH IN UKRAINE

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Subject of research is smart growth.

The aim is to study theoretical and practical aspects of smart growth in Ukraine.

Methods which were used in course of research: method of comparative analysis, generalization, statistical and other research methods.

Study results. Analyzed smart growth in Ukraine. Attention is paid to the priorities and objectives that should be key in the «Europe 2020», and their achievement will be crucial to our success in 2020.

Application of results: Ministry of education and science of Ukraine, Ministry of Finance of Ukraine, the Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine.

Conclusions. *In Ukraine, an important activity of the state and regions should be smart growth, which depends on the capacity of higher education, science, domestic experts, the role of universities in innovative development, technological and industrial development of the regional and national economy.*

Keywords: *smart growth, innovation, globalization, synergies, Strategy for sustainable development «Ukraine – 2020», the European strategy «Europe 2020», framework programme «Horizon 2020».*

Statement of the problem. Regional educational and scientific system, universities are the Foundation of innovative development of the region, a reasonable growth of the country in General and region in particular. Important for smart growth is the implementation of the model «pentaspiral»: education – science – business – government – civil society institutions. What the Pentagon can ensure the success of smart growth, competitiveness of national economy, innovative development.

Analysis of recent researches and publications. The study components, to promote reasonable growth in Ukraine was engaged in such scientists T. Bogolib, B. Danylyshyn, R. Kegel, O. Kratt, L. Semu, L. Fedulova, Y. Vlasov, P. Drucker, V. Kiseleva, G. Kleiner, B.-A. Lundvall, F. Machlup and others.

Presentation of the basic material. Signed by President of Ukraine Decree «On the Strategy for sustainable development «Ukraine – 2020» – a document that has been the focus of the further development of our state for the next five years. That is to say, our «five year plan», based on European experience and backed up by specific indicators, to be achieved over five years.

Deserves attention the very name of this document. Because of the elaboration of a strategy of sustainable development of Ukraine has long and unsuccessfully worked as a research and expert community of our state with the active support of international organizations, various approaches were proposed to the format of the document, its structure and main directions. However, even still, even the definition of the term «sustainable development» is a polemical and includes many different aspects.

Now, given the European integration aspirations of our state, for Ukraine at this stage, the basic document should be the Strategy of sustainable development of the EU. Produced by the European countries in June 2001 and updated in June 2006, the Strategy aims to define and implement measures by which the EU will be able to achieve constant long-term improvement of quality of life by creating sustainable communities able to manage and effectively use natural resources, improve the ecological and social innovation potential of the economy and, in the end able to ensure prosperity, environmental protection and social cohesion [1].

Today, Europe is on the verge of change. The crisis has destroyed years of economic and social progress and revealed structural weaknesses of the European economy. Meanwhile, the world is moving fast and long-term challenges – globalisation, pressure on resources, ageing – intensify.

Europe can have success, if will to act together as a Union. We need a strategy in order to emerge from the crisis stronger and turn the EU into a smart, sustainable and inclusive economy with high levels of employment, productivity and social cohesion.

Three priorities should be the key in the «Europe 2020»:

- Smart growth: developing an economy based on knowledge and innovation.
- Sustainable growth: promoting a more efficient use of resources, the development of more sustainable and competitive economy.

Light growth: promoting an economy with high employment that will contribute to social and territorial cohesion.

These elements complement each other, they offer a vision of social market economy of Europe in the 21st century.

There is a consensus about what direction our efforts and control the progress of the EU should jointly agree on a limited number of key goals for 2020. These objectives should relate to the theme of smart, sustainable and inclusive growth. They must be measurable and reflect the diversity of situations in member States and be based on sufficiently reliable data for purposes of comparison. Based on these criteria were chosen listed below are the goals and their achievement will be crucial to our success in 2020:

- The employment rate of the population aged 20 to 64 should increase from the current 69% to at least 75%, in particular by greater involvement of women, older workers and the better integration of migrants in the workforce.

- Currently, the EU aims to invest 3% of gross domestic product in research activities.

- The EU aims to invest 3% of GDP in research activities. Through this job managed to focus attention on the need to invest public and private sector in research activities, it focuses more on resources than on results. There is a clear need to improve the conditions of private research activities in the EU, and the majority of the measures proposed in this strategy will solve this issue. In addition, the obvious is that if we consider together the research activities and innovations, we get a wider range of costs, which would be more appropriate for business transactions and incentives to improve performance. The Commission proposes to maintain the objective of 3%, while it is necessary to develop a measure that reflects the intensity of research activities and innovation.

- Greenhouse gas emissions must be reduced by at least 20% compared to 1990 levels, or, subject to appropriate conditions, by 30%, increasing the share of renewable energy sources in our final energy consumption to 20% and achieving a 20% increase in efficiency of energy use.

- Achieving goals in education, which is to overcome the problems of availability of persons leaving school, namely, reducing their numbers to 10% compared with the current 15%, while increasing the proportion of the population aged 30-34 years with tertiary education from 31% to at least 40% in 2020.

- The number of citizens living on a certain level below the national poverty line should be reduced by 25%, allowing more than 20 million people to get out of this situation.

These objectives are interdependent. For example, a high level of education is a prerequisite for improving performance and increasing the employment rate helps to reduce poverty. Improving opportunities for research and innovation in all sectors of the economy, combined with increased resource efficiency will improve competitiveness and will stimulate the creation of new jobs. Investing in cleaner, low carbon technologies will help our environment, help combat climate change and create new opportunities for business and employment. These goals should mobilize our collective attention. To change these rules and practices in the EU needs strong leadership, determination and effective mechanism for achieving the objectives to achieve results, aggregated for these purposes.

These objectives are typical, that is, they are not exhaustive. They reflect a shared vision of what the Commission would like to see the EU on key parameters by 2020. They do not reflect the approach «fits all». Each member state is different from each other, and the EU of 27 members is much more diverse than it was ten years ago. Despite the different levels of development and standards of living, the Commission finds that the proposed targets are suitable for all member States – both old and new. Investing in research and innovation, education and technology effective use of resources will benefit traditional sectors, rural areas, and the economy is based on providing high-quality services. This will contribute to the economic, social and territorial cohesion. To ensure that each member state has adopted the strategy «Europe 2020» to their situation, the Commission proposes that EU objectives were reformulated into national targets and ways of achieving them given the current situation of each member state and the level of its aspirations as part of a broader effort by the EU to achieve common goals. In addition to efforts from the member States the Commission will propose a series of drastic measures at EU level designed to bring the EU to a new, more sustainable path of growth. This combination of efforts at European and national level must be complementary [2].

Smart growth – an economy based on knowledge and innovation. Smart growth means strengthening the role of knowledge and innovation as key factors for our future growth. This requires improving the quality of our education, improve research results, promote knowledge transfer and innovation within the Union, making maximum use of information and communication technologies and ensuring the transformation of innovative ideas into new products and services that will promote growth and create quality jobs and solution of European and global social problems. But to succeed, these efforts should be supported by relevant business and financial resources, as well as focusing on customer needs and market opportunities.

Europe needs to take action in the following areas:

- Innovation activities: expenditure on research activities in Europe account for less than 2% compared to 2.6% in USA and 3.4% in Japan, mainly due to the decrease of private investment. You should take into account not only the total volume of expenses for research activities, Europe should also focus on the impact and structure of expenditures on research and to improve the conditions for private sector research activities. A smaller share of high-tech companies explains half explains the difference between our performance and the performance of the United States.

- Education, training and lifelong learning: a quarter of all students having difficulty in reading, one out of every seven people leaves education and training. About 50% of individuals reach a medium level of education, but this is usually insufficient to meet the needs of the labour market. Less than one out of three people aged 25-34 years have higher education, compared with 40% in the US and over 50% in Japan. According to the Shanghai scale only two European universities are among the 20 best in the world.

Digital society: the global demand for information and communication technology is estimated at 2000 billion euros, but only a quarter of this amount comes from the European companies. Europe is also lagging in terms of high speed Internet, which affects its ability to innovate, including in rural areas, as well as dissemination of knowledge via the Internet and e-Commerce products and services.

The result of actions under this priority will accelerate the innovative capacity of Europe, improved outcomes in education, quality and results of educational institutions, as well as the use of economic and social benefits of the digital society. This policy should be implemented at the regional, national and European levels.

Lead initiative «Innovation Union». The purpose of this initiative is to redirect research and innovation policy on the challenges facing our society, such as climate change, energy efficiency and resource efficiency, health and demographic changes. Each link of the innovation chain – from basic research to commercialization – should be strengthened.

At EU level the Commission will work to:

- completion of the European research area, the development program for the strategic research that was focused on issues such as energy security, transport, climate change and resource efficiency, health and ageing, environmentally friendly production methods and land management, as well as on the activation of joint programmes with member States and regions;

- to improve framework conditions for business innovation (namely, the creation of a single EU patent and a specialised patent court, modernise the framework for copyright and trademarks, improve access to the protection of intellectual property and accelerate the introduction of standards compatibility, improved access to capital and efficient use of the policy of demand management, for example, through tendering and prudential regulation);

- the introduction of the «European partnerships for innovation» between the EU and national levels to accelerate the development and deployment of technologies that are needed to solve the identified problems. The first of these will

include: the development of the Bioeconomy until 2020», «key technologies that will shape the industrial future of Europe» and «technologies that allow elderly people to live independently and to be an active part of society»;

- strengthening and further developing the role of EU instruments for promoting innovation (e.g. structural funds, Fund for rural development, framework programme research activities, Program development innovation (CIP), Strategic energy technology plan (SET Plan)), in particular through closer cooperation with the European investment Bank and the simplification of administrative procedures, which should facilitate access to Finance, particularly for small and medium enterprises and implementation of innovative incentive mechanisms linked to the carbon market, in particular for those who reaches their goals faster;

- development of partnerships for the exchange of knowledge and strengthening the ties between education, economic activity, research and innovation, in particular through the EIT, and to promote entrepreneurship by providing support to young innovative enterprises.

At the national level, member States should:

- to reform national (and regional) research and innovation activities to promote high quality and reasonable specialization, strengthening cooperation between universities, cooperation between science and business activities, joint programmes and strengthening cooperation in the areas of value-added of the EU and the respective national funding procedures and ensure the dissemination of technologies throughout the EU;

- provide sufficient number of experts from natural Sciences, mathematical Sciences and engineering and to focus school curricula on the development of creativity, innovation and entrepreneurship;

- to prioritize spending on knowledge, in particular through the use of tax incentives and other financial instruments to promote greater private investment in research activities.

Lead initiative: «youth on the move». The aim is to improve the results achieved in higher education in Europe and make it more attractive for the world community, and enhance the overall quality of education and training in the EU at all levels by combining experience and equality, increasing the mobility of students and trainees and to improve the situation of employment of young people.

At EU level the Commission will work to:

- to integrate and enhance exchange programs in the EU, University and research programmes (e.g. Erasmus, Erasmus Mundus, Tempus and Marie Curie), as well as to create a link between them and the national programs and resources;

- to intensify the programme for the modernisation of higher education (curricula, governance and financing) including the comparison of results of universities and educational outcomes in a global context;

- explore the development of entrepreneurship through exchange programs for young professionals;

- to promote recognition of formal and informal learning;

- to develop a framework for ensuring youth employment, will outline strategies aimed at reducing unemployment among young people: it will contribute, together with member States and social partners, entry of young people into the labour market through training, practice and other forms of receiving work experience, including through a scheme («Your first job with EURES») aimed at expanding employment opportunities for young people through the promotion of mobility in the EU.

At the national level, member States should:

- to ensure efficient investment in education and vocational training system at all levels (from preschool to University);

- to improve performance in education, paying attention to each segment (pre-school, primary, secondary and higher education) in the framework of an integrated approach, encompassing key competences and is directed at reducing the early dropout;

- to enhance the openness and relevance of education systems by building national qualification frameworks and better coordination of educational outcomes to labour market needs;

- to improve young people's access to the labour market on the basis of integrated activities, particularly leadership, consultation and training.

Lead initiative: «the Program in the field of digital technologies for Europe». The goal is to obtain sustainable economic and social benefits of a digital single market based on fast and high-speed Internet connection and compatible programs that allow broad access to the Internet for all by 2013, access for all to high-speed Internet (at least 30 Mbps) until 2020 and the signing of at least 50% of European families have an Internet connection faster than 100 Mbit/sec.

At EU level the Commission will work to:

- is to provide reliable legal framework which encourages investment in open and competitive high speed Internet infrastructure and related services;

- to develop spectral efficient policy;

- facilitate the use of EU structural funds to achieve the objectives of the programme;

- to create a truly single market for online content and services (including unlimited secure European network services and digital content markets), with a high level of confidence, a balanced regulatory framework, with a clear regime of human rights, the promotion of bitterfield issuance of licenses, the provision of adequate protection and remuneration of rights holders and active support for the digitization of the rich cultural heritage of the EU and to establish the concept of global control of the Internet;

- to reform the research funding and innovation, and increase financial support in the field of information and communication technologies to improve the technological strength of Europe in key strategic areas and create the conditions for small and medium enterprises, which are developing, have occupied key positions in the emerging markets, and promote innovation of information and communication technologies in all economic sectors;

- to promote Internet access and use of the Internet by all European citizens, especially through actions that will promote literacy in digital technologies and accessibility of the Internet.

At the national level, member States should:

- to develop operational strategies for high speed Internet access, and focus public funding, in particular structural funds, to areas whose needs are not fully met by private investments;

- to create a legal framework to coordinate state activities to reduce expenditure on network development ;

- encourage the use of modern accessible online services (such as e-government, e-portal health», «smart house», digital competence, security) [2].

The development strategy for Europe aimed at the harmonious development of the three vertices of the so-called «triangle of knowledge» (knowledge triangle) – education, research and innovation, which involves strong support from the state and society, as well as the corresponding stimulation levels of human activity in the areas of traditional knowledge production and competitive products [3].

This principle resonates with the concept of triple helix (Triple Helix) interactions between universities, government and the business sector in the framework of the innovation system. This concept was proposed in 1990-ies Professor at Stanford University (USA) Henry Ckout and his colleague Last Leydesdorff from Amsterdam. Coca approach is based on the fact that in modern society the core innovative activity is the University that started collaborating closely with the business, doing research for them and creating a flow of know-how with a view to continuous improvement of products and services produced by this business. In this model, the University becomes the main focal point for the government efforts and resources for innovation. This kind of University called the research [4], or, as they aptly call Covc, – «business» [5]. Of course, a research University retains all academic component, but it works on the principle of «the knowledge triangle» simultaneously in three interrelated areas: education, research, innovative technologies and bring them to market (technology transfer).

Some researchers believe that the concept of «triple helix» we are talking about a mutual penetration and inseparable connection of the various components of the innovation system, each of which (not just University) is playing his or her specific role. Moreover, the concept of «triple helix» can have various modifications.

For example, in some countries, public sector research and development plays such a significant role that the state acts as a regulator of science and innovation activities (according to the original interpretation of the concept of Triple Helix) and active «player», along with the business sector and institutions of higher education. This flexible approach to the assessment of cooperation in the sphere of science, education and innovation is no objection to the vast majority of specialists [6].

The implementation of the concept of «knowledge triangle» provided on the idea of synergism (synergy) or «synergistic effect» – joint action to achieve a common goal based on the principle that the whole is more than the sum of its parts [7]. Synergy means the excess of the aggregate of the sum of the factors. So, the income from the joint use of resources that exceed the amount of revenues from the use of the same resources individually. Synergies between the activities of individual strategic units involves the search for resources and capabilities, complementing and reinforcing their efforts to achieve greater results in comparison with the case where they act autonomously.

A synergistic effect may occur through the transfer of technologies, know-how, sharing of resources, creating advantages in consistency of the timing of individual projects, the increase in quality, increase consumer confidence in the final result. In General, synergistic effects can be described by three variables: the increase in profit in monetary terms, reduced operational costs and lower investment requirements [7]. All variables are inextricably linked with time. Therefore, the fourth synergistic effect can be considered the acceleration of change of these variables.

Thus it is the synergy of «knowledge triangle» allows for the most effective to ensure the interaction of education, science and innovation, receiving effective result in the form of development of innovative infrastructure, mechanisms and models for its implementation, improving the quality of educational services, their competitiveness, maximizing the productivity of research and development, commercialization, provision of additional revenue (profit) from sale of intellectual property (intellectual products) for universities, educational and research institutions, technology transfer.

An extremely important role in this process belongs to universities, in particular, not just a classic academic institutions and modern research universities, with developed innovation infrastructure. The mission of research universities is to train high-quality human capital through the use of advanced multidisciplinary research, creating a holistic learning process in accordance with the «triangle of knowledge». This involves strengthening the fundamental component of the training and scientific research, and the dissemination multidisciplinares, openness and mobility training systems, raising the status of separate disciplines [3]; education, development and support of the creative component of the personality of the researcher-the scientist-entrepreneur.

It should also be noted that one of the important and necessary criteria for the implementation of the «knowledge triangle» as a strategic direction of development of European education is openness and sharing of knowledge as a consequence of the implementation of openness and mobility training systems. European experts have declared that the criterion of «freedom of movement of knowledge» as the «fifth freedom» («fifth freedom») [8] – in continuation of a list of fundamental European values, «the four freedoms of the EU», which recognized a

common market, free movement, dwelling and employment of citizens. Initiatives aimed at the implementation of the «fifth freedom» and the development of European Space for Research and Innovation («ERA»), with a view to facilitating such exchanges across borders.

Development «open innovation» reflects the fact that their own business and companies increasingly difficult to «afford» a private research and development. They must use knowledge and technologies developed by universities and research centers. In addition, they often need to cooperate with other companies, including competitors. In search of ideas, solutions, technologies and best partners of the company must look beyond national borders.

Some of the initiatives formed a common understanding of the different actors in research and innovation (large firms, SMEs, universities, research centers, etc.) need to maintain their cooperation throughout the EU and beyond. For example the initiative on knowledge transfer and intellectual property office or the European technology platform [9] that bring together participants from all over Europe in specific industries and technologies.

Transnational research cooperation is also supported by funding programmes, particularly EU framework Programmes. They support a large number of transnational projects, studies, large-scale initiatives that pool resources across Europe and beyond around common goals. For example, joint technology initiatives combining private and public funding, researchers from companies and universities to solve complex technological tasks [10]. The involvement of small and medium-sized enterprises in the realization of the main objectives of the initiatives complement the framework programme for competitiveness and innovation (Competitiveness and Innovation Framework Programme – CIP) EU framework Programme that supports innovation activities (including eco-innovation) [10], providing better access to Finance and provides business support in the regions.

The experience of Ukraine shows that the implementation of the «knowledge triangle» in the domestic environment becomes the real objective requirement. For many decades, educational institutions in our country was formed exclusively as institutions, not institutions for scientific research and its commercialization. Transformations in science in isolation from changes in the economy are meaningless [11].

The Ministry of education and science confronts institutions of higher education target: all applied studies have ended with the commercialization or licensing agreement, or *hozdogovornyh* relations that would provide for the implementation of those or other works and would allow universities to earn money. High results of the commercialization of a predominantly institutions, which are about 30% – fundamental research, the rest of the application [11].

Of course, in the implementation of these requirements has become very important universities with research status (self-governing), which in Ukraine 14 [11], most among which are the Polytechnic universities of Kiev, Kharkiv, Lviv, Dnieper, Lugansk, Burg. Research University – national institution of higher education that has a significant scientific achievements, conducts research and innovative activities, ensures the integration of education and science with industry, and participates in international projects and programmes. The status of the research provided the University with the aim of increasing its role as a center of education and science, training highly qualified scientific and scientific-pedagogical personnel, introduction of scientific achievements, implementation of joint programs in priority areas of research to address important socio-economic tasks in different sectors of the economy.

Positive domestic practice testifies to the possibility of the implementation of the European concept of the «knowledge triangle» on the basis of universities and their cooperation with enterprises and business in spite of the systemic problems of transformation. In addition to the activities of research universities in Ukraine has successful experience of functioning of science parks at universities, which are based on the shared interests of the parties to unite foreign and Ukrainian companies, scientific working groups and laboratories that provide them with a competitive stream know-how, engineering and technical courses that prepare companies for high quality staff, venture and investment funds, that are investors in start-up projects (start-up projects).

The work of science parks attracting more and more students who not only work in their companies, but also create the structure of the business incubators of their own small companies to market their inventions and projects – innovations [12].

An important activity of the state and regions should be a reasonable growth.

The latest achievements of science, education, culture and social policy, innovative vector of socio-economic development of the country and the regions requires a more complete use of the potential of higher education, academic staff, ensure high quality, increase of stability and competitiveness in accordance with the requirements of the globalized world.

XXI century can rightly be considered the century of education, science, knowledge, because the public sphere is evolving and will require deep transformations in connection with transition to a postindustrial society. In addition to the traditional tasks – the education, training and research, higher education, universities must implement its educational and cultural mission to play the intellectual and spiritual potential of the nation, to integrate into the global innovation space. The University should be the basis of smart growth.

In Ukraine there are all conditions for their development, there is a problem, and who needs them? The market of scientific production develops slowly, the Ukrainian scientist became an academic entrepreneur. In our opinion, and it coincides with the opinion of foreign scientists G. Ackoff, Becca, M. Vlasova, V. Drucker, I. Dino, G. Craner, F. Maluta, I. Moses, E. Popova, Yu. a. Urmantsev the basis for smart growth at the country level and the region should be the universities. In addition to the traditional tasks – the education, training and research, higher education, universities must implement its educational and cultural mission to play the intellectual and spiritual potential of the nation, to integrate into the global innovation space.

Regional educational and scientific system, universities are the basis for innovative development. Important for the development of the country in General and region in particular has an implementation of the model «pentacel»: education – science – business – government – civil society institutions. This Pentagon scientists of the Ural state economic University will ensure the success of the regional development of the state, competitiveness of the national economy and the economy of regions, their innovation development. The main problem of implementation n ticotico financial resources, therefore, we believe that in the context of globalization and cooperation of Ukrainian scientists should participate in the implementation of the European strategy «Europe 2020» framework program «Horizon 2020».

Innovations of the national economy, regional economies, Ukraine should use the scientific potential of universities.

University – centre of education and science, scientific research is the Foundation of its activities. Universities should have on the contemporary stage a significant impact on the state of the national economy of Ukraine, but universities have not fully performed their mission in the economic development of the country.

Important to elevate the role of universities in national economic development, innovation processes, globalization and cooperation adopted in 2009 the Law of Ukraine «On scientific parks» [13]. This law regulates legal and economic relations connected with the establishment and operation of scientific parks, and is aimed at intensification of the processes of development, implementation, production of innovative products and innovative products on domestic and foreign markets. Science Park – a legal entity created at the initiative of the institution of higher education and/or research institutions by pooling of contributions of the founders to control the processes of elaboration and implementation of projects of the scientific Park.

The science Park is created with the aim of developing scientific-technical and innovation activities in higher education and/or scientific institution and national effective use of existing scientific potential, material and technical base for commercialization of scientific researches and their implementation on domestic and foreign markets.

The famous economist I. Moses said: «Universities should contribute to the prosperity, enrichment of society, culture and economy. Fulfilling its role of custodians, creators and disseminators of knowledge, universities contribute to the enrichment of people and society which they are part. They should strive to put their intellectual potential at the service of society [14].

Scientific and technological developments of Ukrainian scientists should be adequately represented on the European market of scientific production, technological development and can be used to achieve global social goals.

Implementation of the model «pentadbiran», Ukraine's accession to the European strategy «Europe 2020 and the framework programme «Horizon 2020» will provide an opportunity for the integrated management of processes of innovative activities: generation, transmission, application of new scientific knowledge, the creation on their basis of naukovoyi technologies [14]. The main «pentadbiran» science, education, business, and the Central figure is an innovative people. All parts interact through man. Through the prism of «pentadbiran» in Ukraine can revive scientific and innovative activities. Through the prism of possible implementation models «pentadbiran» in Ukraine to revive the market of scientific production, its implementation in the foreign market.

Important activities of Ukrainian universities is the development of strategies and tactics the use of intellectual property institutions of higher education, is a promising development, cooperation with enterprises and scientific centers of the region, experience exchange with similar structures in units of other higher education institutions.

For the effective implementation of the process of commercialization of scientific research at the University required innovative process control system of commercialization of scientific developments and promising projects.

Technoparks innovation in high-tech production, to realize scientific development that gives you the ability to be powerful sources of extrabudgetary funds to those institutions of higher education under which they operate, as by themselves they are strong businesses.

The situation in the universities of Ukraine today is characterized by the following factors:

- no doubt the high innovation potential of the universities of Ukraine;
- in universities (especially in engineering) have gained new experience of implementation of developments in the industry, has created a number of services and units aimed at supporting this process (patent-information departments, design offices, computer centers, pilot production);
- in recent years in most universities with the aim of commercialization of completed research under the departments and divisions have been created and have shown sufficient efficiency in modern conditions of small innovative firms of different ownership forms; in several universities with the aim of creating an environment of support for small companies was created by business incubators, technological parks, innovative-technological centers;
- there has been a sustained interest of students to new ways of organizing research and application of its results in the market nowcome products.

In universities there are all the positive terms related to the implementation of research and development, transforming the results and knowledge into a commercial product by passing it on to the market of scientific and technical products, training in the field of innovation management. Universities of Ukraine have the necessary space for entrepreneurial projects. At the same time, there are conditions for the creation of small technology firms, which could be the property of University employees. For overseas small firms engaged in technology transfer that are created in scientific groups, providing a profit from the sale of new high-tech product. International experience shows that promoting research and development through small firm costs about two times cheaper and is realized two times faster than if doing a large University.

The creation and development of Technopark of the University will provide the following tasks:

- preservation of the scientific potential of the University (jobs in innovative structures);
- creating an experimental base for support and retraining of specialists in the field of economy of knowledge-intensive entrepreneurship;
- creation of conditions for commercialization of applied research, bringing their results to the product offered on the market of high technology products;
- enable better access to extrabudgetary funding sources, including venture capital;
- strengthening of cooperation with the region by connecting to the solution of problems of development of the industry;
- development of cooperative relations with the regions;
- the development of international relations in the training;
- experts in the field of knowledge-intensive entrepreneurship, the implementation of joint innovation projects;
- intellectual property protection for generated knowledge-intensive products and services;
- access to the international market of high-tech products [15].

In Ukraine developed and adopted a significant number of legislative and regulatory documents aimed at the development of market research products and technologies, but they become an effective tool of commercialization of scientific development due to lack of demand in the domestic market and lack of access to external markets of scientific products and technologies.

The signing of the Treaty of Ukraine on Association with the European Union will allow Ukraine to join the Program «Europe 2020», in the framework of a reasonable growth factor to enter the European market of scientific developments and technologies. The industry needs to modernize, the new industrialization. Most industries are in the 4th and 5th technological structures, so there is a need for introduction of scientific development, because this way will enable the economy to grow based on innovation and have a competitive national economy.

The market of scientific developments of universities in Ukraine has prospects of development.

Features of development of modern civilization determines the development of a network of institutions of higher education as a technical-material base formation of all components of the potential of higher education and especially educational and vocational aspects. The University has a leading role in the production, dissemination and transfer of knowledge in modern society.

The University provides the integration of science, education, business, government and civil society as the basis of modernization of economy.

Knowledge as the main resource of production relations, especially the formation of a knowledge economy, institutions of the knowledge economy is described in detail in the monograph Is.In. Popov and A. V. Vlasov «Institutions of knowledge» [16].

Conclusions. If these conditions are optimal for Ukraine is accession to the European strategy «Europe 2020» framework program «Horizon 2020». This will contribute to reasonable growth, innovation, globalization, integration, cooperation.

Because Approval of a sustainable development Strategy «Ukraine – 2020», under certain circumstances, can and must become the driving force, which not only will bring our country to European best practices for sustainable development, but also will contribute to the early recovery from the economic crisis.

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